

We2-1-3: Tuning Silicon Implantation for alpha-Ga₂O₃ and beta-Ga₂O₃ MESFET Transistors

Authors: Aniol Vellvehi¹, Pierre Gallarday¹, Edgars Butanovs², Ekaterine Chikoizde³, Zeyu Chi³, Jose Rebollo¹, Miquel Vellvehi¹, Amador Perez-Tomas¹

¹ The Institute of Microelectronics of Barcelona (IMB-CNM-CSIC), Campus UAB, Bellaterra, 08193 Barcelona, Spain, Barcelona, Spain

² Institute of Solid State Physics UL, Kengaraga iela 8, LV-1063 Riga, Latvia, Riga, Latvia

³ Groupe d'Etude de la Matière Condensée, Université Paris-Saclay GEMaC, UVSQ – CNRS, 45 Av. des Etats-Unis, 78035 Cedex Versailles, France, Paris, France

Abstract:

Gallium oxide (Ga₂O₃) exists in multiple polymorphic forms, with the most prominent being the alpha (α) and beta (β) phases. The β-phase of Ga₂O₃ is the most thermodynamically stable form at ambient conditions. It crystallizes in a monoclinic structure and features a mixture of gallium atoms in tetrahedral and octahedral coordination with oxygen. This phase has a band gap in the range of approximately 4.8 to 4.9 electron volts. Due to its stability and relatively wide band gap, β-Ga₂O₃ is widely used in power electronics, ultraviolet photodetectors, and as a transparent conductive oxide. It can be grown using bulk methods such as the Czochralski process, edge-defined film-fed growth (EFG), and also via chemical vapor deposition and molecular beam epitaxy. In contrast, the α-phase of Ga₂O₃ is metastable at ambient pressure and temperature, meaning it is not the naturally favored form under standard conditions. However, it can be stabilized as thin films or under high pressure. This phase adopts a rhombohedral crystal structure, similar to that of α-alumina (α-Al₂O₃), with all gallium atoms occupying octahedral sites. The band gap of α-Ga₂O₃ is slightly wider than that of the β-phase, typically ranging from 5.2 to 5.3 electron volts. α-Ga₂O₃ is primarily of interest for thin-film applications, including ultraviolet detectors and high-voltage electronic devices. It is generally synthesized using deposition techniques such as metal-organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD), pulsed laser deposition (PLD), or sputtering. In this work, we use the Al₂O₃ ALD cap method reported by Jena and co-workers [1] to develop Si implanted layers which can be annealed at the same temperature than on beta-phase to activate Si doping. In the final paper, we will discuss the basic building blocks (drift conductivity, Ohmic contact, Activation, etc.) as well as the device performances.

[1] J.P. McCandless, D. Jena, et al. *Thermal stability of epitaxial α-Ga₂O₃ and (Al,Ga)₂O₃ layers on m-plane sapphire*, Appl. Phys. Lett. 119, 062102 (2021); doi: 10.1063/5.0064278